

MULTI-COLORED SOLAR PANELS - NEW POSSIBILITIES FOR DESIGN OF ENERGY-EFFICIENT BUILDINGS.

Senior teacher **Uzboyev M.D.**, student **Uralov R.**
Samarkand state architecture – construction university named after M.Ulugbek

Annotatsiya: Zamonaviy shaharlarni barpo etishda asosiy etiborni binoraning dizayniga va undagi qo'llanilgan zamonaviy texnologiyalarni etiborga olinadi. Binolarni tashqi ko'rinishiga bezak berishda har-xil ko'rinishdagi qo'rilish materiallaridan foydalaniladi. Ushbu materiallar o'rniga, quyoshdan quvvat oluvchi batareya va kollektorlardan foydalanilsa binoning energiya tejamkorligi va ekologik toza binolar barpo etsa bo'ladi.

Kalit so'zlar: mikrometr, kremniy qalinligi, yarim o'tkazgich, o'tkazuvchan oksid, quyosh energiyasini o'zgartirgichlar, quyosh panellari, qora yoki kulrang quyosh panellari.

Annotation: In the construction of modern cities, the main attention is paid to the design of the building and the modern technologies used in it. Construction materials of various types are used to decorate the exterior of buildings. Instead of these materials, if solar batteries and collectors are used, it is possible to build energy-saving and environmentally friendly buildings.

Key words: Micrometer, thickness silicon, semiconductor, conductive oxide, solar energy converters, solar panels, black or gray solar panels.

Until now, designers could only use black or gray solar panels for the facades and roofs of buildings, especially not to be chosen.

The installation of standard solar panels for the production of electricity on the roofs and facades of buildings significantly changes the appearance of buildings, and not always for the better. At the moment, only dark solar panels are widely represented on the market.

However, now, thanks to a high-tech thin film, the developers were able to turn solar energy elements into colorful panels, providing great scope for creativity. "So far, enough work has been done to integrate solar energy converters and design elements, which would enable us to create individual design solutions," says Kevin Fuchsel, manager of the Fraunhofer Institute for Applied Optics and Precision Engineering in Jena, Germany.

But the state of things is changing for the better. The physicists of the research institute have been working for four years on the development of solar cells with a nanostructure that could be produced for the mass market. Together with the team of researchers at the Fraunhofer Institute, scientists from the University of Friedrich Schiller in Jena are developing inexpensive production technologies that will not only increase the efficiency of solar batteries, but also significantly expand the possibilities for designers and architects.

Silicone plates, thick with a paper sheet, will color the solar panels in different colors. K. Fuchsel is currently working on the creation of multicolored solar cells based on the finest silicone wafers, no thicker than a sheet of paper. Such batteries will provide space for creativity in the decoration of facades and roofs of houses.

How it works: A silicone semiconductor, only a few micrometers thick, absorbs sunlight and turns it into electricity. In order for a large amount of light to flow to the silicone substrate, the semiconductor layer is provided with an optically neutral protective barrier

(insulator), on which an oxide layer with a thickness of one hundred nanometers is applied.

This translucent conductive oxide (ACO) conducts electricity, it is necessary in order to collect and direct as many light particles as possible onto the semiconductor layer below.

SPO has a lower reflective index, compared with silicone, so it works as an antireflection coating.

The simple design of such a SIS (semiconductor insulator-semiconductor) solar cell, with a transparent top layer, has several advantages: in addition to the fact that such a panel is capable of collecting more sunlight, it can also be made in different colors and shapes.

Project of the facade of the building using designer solar panels.

Color varies due to the change in the thickness of the transparent layer of conductive oxide, which affects its reflective index. Thus, the researchers were able to connect the silicone plates with converters of sunlight, the thickness of the film.

They also managed to move forward in the use of innovative coating materials. Oxide India-Tin is the most common material to date, but it is quite expensive. Researchers are working on the use of cheaper zinc oxide with the addition of aluminum, which will significantly reduce the cost of production, and offer more favorable prices to consumers.

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